

Extreme rainfall indices and climate change of Vadodara city

Chirayu Pandit¹, Dr.Sanskriti Mujumdar², Akash Patel³

1Lecturer, Department of Civil Engineering, Polytechnic, The M.S.University of Baroda, Vadodara 390002,India, 2Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The M.S.University of Baroda, Vadodara 390001,India. 3Research Assistant, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The M.S.University of Baroda, Vadodara 390001

e-mail: pandit.chirayu-polyced@msubaroda.ac.in, sanskritimujumdar@yahoo.co.in, akash.patel-ced@msubaroda.ac.in

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Abstract:

Climate can be defined from average of long term meteorological parameters of the region but to understand climate change extreme values are more helpful. World Meteorological Organisation has identified indices related to extreme rainfall which have impacts on health, agriculture and food security, water resources and hydrology sectors. Vadodara (22.28 N, 73.19E) is the third largest city of Gujarat and eighteenth largest city of India with urban population greater than 1.6 million. Daily rainfall data for Vadodara station from 1961-2016 is collected from State Water Data Centre, Gandhinagar. Annual trends for heavy precipitation days (R10mm, R20mm), extreme precipitation days (R95P), Contribution of extreme precipitation in annual rainfall (R95PT) annual total wet-day precipitation (PRCPTOT), consecutive dry days (CDD), consecutive wet days (CWD), one day maximum rainfall (Rx1), maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation (Rx5) and Standardized Daily Intensity Index (SDII) for the study period were calculated with Mann Kendall test. Generally increasing trend is observed for all indices except CWD, CDD and R95p where no trend is observed. Observed annual magnitudes of one day & five days maximum rainfall (Rx1day and Rx5days) are increasing significantly (p value < 0.05). Daily rainfall intensity (SDII) also shows significant increasing trend. All the indices indicate that high rainfall with shorter duration is increasing for Vadodara city. The observed trends of extreme indices confirm the impact of climate change on rainfall pattern of Vadodara.

Introduction

Cities concentrate wealth, people, and productivity, but they also concentrate vulnerability to natural disasters and to long-term changes in climate. Rising sea levels will affect millions of people living in coastal cities. Similarly, migration, changes in land use, and spatial development are likely to increase the vulnerability of populations to changes in weather and climatic conditions. Adaptation to climate change is therefore an imperative for cities, as it is for the world at large. The urgency of this challenge is also evident when considering the massive investments in buildings and infrastructure that cities in developing countries will undertake in the coming years, which will lock in urban form and structure for many decades thereafter. (Hoornweg, et al. 2011)

Synthesis report of IPCC (Pachauri, et al. 2014) concluded that the changes in many extreme weather and climate events have been observed since 1950. Some of these changes have been linked to human influences, including a decrease in cold temperature extremes, an increase in warm temperature extremes, an increase in extreme high sea levels and an increase in the number of heavy precipitation events in a number of regions.

Standardization of extremity of the weather event can help in uniform assessment of climate change. To quantitatively reflect an extreme precipitation event, it should be complemented by characterization with the metrics like magnitude, duration, severity and extent. (L. V. Alexander 2015)

Study of extreme rainfall during south west monsoon all over India (Pattanaik and Rajeevan 2010) during 1951-2005 observed that the occurrence of extreme rainfall events (rainfall >124.4 mm in a day) over India during the southwest monsoon season shows spatial variability with preferred regions of occurrence over the entire west coast of India, parts of central India and parts of northeast India also the frequency of extreme rainfall shows a significant increasing trend over the Indian monsoon region

129 rain gauge stations across India were analysed over the period of 1910 to 2000 by (Sen Roy and Balling 2004). annual time series of seven different indices of extreme precipitation events, including total precipitation, largest 1, 5, and 30 day totals, and the number of daily events above the amount that marks the 90th, 95th, and 97.5th percentiles of all precipitation at each station. The analysis concluded that there was increase in the frequency of extreme precipitation events over the study period.

Study area

Vadodara (22.28 N, 73.19E), the third largest city of Gujarat and eighteenth largest city of India, is situated at Altitude 35.5 m. above mean sea level on the banks of river vishvamitri in Gujarat state. (Figure 1) The topography of the city is relatively flat, with the ground mildly sloping from northeast to southwest.

Area of Vadodara city is around 159.95 Sq.Kms having population of 16.6 lakh while Vadodara district is spread over 7794 Sq. Kms Area with 36.5 lakh population. Entire region falls under semi-arid climate.

Climate of the Vadodara city is characterized by hot and arid from Southwest Monsoon season Dry throughout the year. Average annual Rainfall is 806 mm. Average annual Rainy days are 37. Mean monthly highest rainfall observed in July is 267 mm. Mean monthly lowest rainfall observed in February is 1 mm. Ever recorded heaviest rainfall in 24 Hrs. is 297 mm on 01 July 2005. Rainfall during the southwest monsoon season is about 94% of Annual rainfall.

Figure 1 Study Area Vadodara City

Data

It may be noted that for extreme rainfall analysis for studying the behavior of changes in the extreme events using of real or actual station data is more realistic than the gridded data as in the later case extreme events will be missed in most of the occasions due to interpolation or averaging scheme used in gridding. This even mislead regarding the signals of hydrological extremes for better disaster management. (Guhathakurta, Menon, et al. 2010)

Data of daily rainfall of Vadodara station for data length 1961-2016 is collected from State Water Data Centre (SWDC) Gandhinagar.

Method

The Expert Team on Sector-specific Climate Indices (ET-SCI) indices related to daily precipitation characteristics are analyzed in the present study. Climate indices provide valuable information contained in daily data, without the need to transmit the daily data itself. For this reason indices derived from daily data are an attempt to objectively extract information from daily weather observations to answer questions concerning aspects of the climate system that affect many human and natural systems with particular emphasis on extremes (Alexander and Herold 2015). Indices related to precipitation and analyzed for Vadodara are described in Table 1.

Table 1 ET-SCI extreme precipitation indices

Code	Indicator name	Description	Unit
R10	Number of heavy precipitation days	Annual count of days when rainfall ≥ 10 mm	Days
R20	Number of very heavy precipitation days	Annual count of days when rainfall ≥ 20 mm	Days
RX1day	Maximum 1-day precipitation amount	Annual maximum 1-day precipitation	mm
Rx5day	Maximum 5-day precipitation amount	Annual maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation	mm
R95p	Very wet days	Annual total PRCP when daily rainfall > 95 th percentile	mm
PRCPTOT	Annual total wet-day precipitation	Annual total precipitation in wet days (daily rainfall ≥ 1 mm)	mm
SDII	Simple daily intensity index	Annual total precipitation divided by the number of wet days (defined as daily rainfall ≥ 1.0 mm) in the year	mm day ⁻¹
R95PT	Annual contribution from very wet days	$(R95p/PRCPTOT) \times 100$	%
CDD	Consecutive dry days	Maximum number of consecutive days with rainfall < 1 mm	Days
CWD	Consecutive wet days	Maximum number of consecutive days with rainfall ≥ 1 mm	Days

Trend Analysis

Temporal trend determination is an important part of data analysis. Trend analysis will indicate whether sample values are increasing or decreasing over time. In addition, an estimate of the trend's magnitude can help to determine whether a statistically significant trend is of practical concern. Trend over the study period of all indices were calculated by Mann kendall Test.

Mann Kendall Test

Mann (1945) presented nonparametric test for randomness against time which constitutes a particular application of Kendall's test for correlation (1975) known as Mann Kendall or Kendall t – test.

Non-parametric Mann-Kendall method is widely used to analyze the trends of the environmental time series, which is recommended by World Meteorological Organization (WMO). In the Mann-Kendall test, missing values are allowed and the data need not conform to any particular distribution.

In the computation of this statistical test the normal approximation (Z statistics). For time series with 10 or more data points the normal approximation is used. The number of annual values in the studied data series is denoted by n. Missing values are allowed and n can thus be smaller than the number of years in the studied time series.

$$S = \sum_{i=2}^n \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \text{sign}(x_i - x_j) \quad \{\text{Eqn. 1}\}$$

where $\text{sign}(x_i - x_j)$ is

-1 for $x_i - x_j < 0$

0 for $x_i - x_j = 0$

1 for $x_i - x_j > 0$

First, the variance of S is computed by the following equation, which takes into account that ties may be present:

$$\text{VAR}(S) = \frac{1}{18} \left[n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{p=1}^q t_p(t_p-1)(2t_p+5) \right] \quad \{\text{Eqn. 2}\}$$

Here q is the number of tied groups and t_p is the number of data values in the pth group. The values of S and $\text{Var}(S)$ are used to compute the test statistic Z as follows

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{(S-1)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & S > 0 \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{(S+1)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & S < 0 \end{cases} \quad \{\text{Eqn. 3}\}$$

The presence of a statistically significant trend is evaluated using the Z value. A positive value of Z indicates an upward trend while negative value denote downward trend. The statistic Z has a normal distribution. Sen's slope method is used to derive magnitude of the slope.

Analysis and Results

Absolute indices represented maximum or minimum values of weather parameters within a season or year. The absolute precipitation indices are maximum 1-day precipitation amount (RX1day), maximum 5-day precipitation amount (RX5day) for a year. The result shows significant (0.05 level) positive trend for Rx1day and Rx5days with p value 0.046 and 0.008 respectively. Sen's slope indicates that there is an annual rise of 0.92 mm and 1.74 mm in Rx1day and Rx5days respectively. (Figure 2 c,d)

Threshold indices are defined as the number of days at which temperature or precipitation value falls above or below a fixed threshold number of heavy precipitation days >10 mm (R10), very heavy precipitation days > 20 mm (R20) and extremely wet days when rainfall is above 95 percentile rainfall for Vadodara the threshold value is 74 mm. Positive non significant trend is observed for R10 with annual rise of

0.093 days (Figure 2-a). Similarly very heavy precipitation days (R20) increases non significantly with the rate of 0.077 days per year (Figure 2-b). No trend is observed for extremely wet days. (Figure 2-e)

Table 2 Extreme Rainfall Indices for Vadodara City

Indices Code	Kendall's tau	p-value	Sen's slope
R10 (Days)	0.135	0.152	0.093
R20 (Days)	0.143	0.132	0.077
Rx1day (mm)	0.185	0.046	0.929
Rx5days (mm)	0.246	0.008	1.744
R95p (Days)	0.100	0.312	0.000
R95PT (%)	0.107	0.249	0.167
PRCPTOT (mm)	0.114	0.216	4.021
SDII (mm/day)	0.304	0.001	0.133
CDD (Days)	0.034	0.721	0.000
CWD (Days)	-0.060	0.530	0.000

Duration indices consist of consecutive dry days (CDD) and consecutive wet days (CWD). The CDD index is the length of the longest dry spell in a year while the CWD index is defined as the longest wet spell in a year; No increasing or decreasing trend is observed for CWD and CDD. (Figure 2- i, j)

Other indices include indices of annual precipitation total (PRCPTOT), Contribution of Extreme rainfall in total rainfall (R95PT) and simple daily intensity index (SDII). Though no trend is observed in extremely wet days, the contribution of extreme rainfall is increasing non significantly at the rate of 0.16% annually. (Figure 2-f) Annual total rainfall (PRCPTOT) shows non significant increasing trend (Figure 2-g) at the rate of 4.02 mm /year. Simple daily intensity index (SDII) observed significant increasing trend with p value 0.001. SDII increases 0.133 mm/day per year. Calculated Kendall's tau, p value and Sen's slope for all indices can be referred from Table 1 Table 2. The total rainfall, contribution of extreme rainfall and daily intensity increasing over the study period of 56 years which point out towards the climate change at local level.

Figure 2 Extreme Rainfall Indices Trends for Vadodara

Conclusion

Extreme daily precipitation characteristics of Vadodara city are explored through the indices suggested by the Expert Team on Sector-specific Climate Indices (ET-SCI). Trend for each index was found with non parametric Mann kendall test and Sen's slope method.

Annual rainy days with heavy rainfall (R10 & R20) are increasing non significantly, no trend is observed for rainy days with extreme rainfall (R95). Consecutive dry days (CDD) show decreasing non significant trend while no trend is observed for consecutive wet days (CWD).

Total annual rainfall (PRCPTOT) shows non significant increasing trend, similarly contribution of extreme rainfall in total annual rainfall (R95PT) is also showing increasing trend.

Observed annual magnitudes of one day & five days maximum rainfall (Rx1day and Rx5days) are increasing significantly. Daily rainfall intensity (SDII) also shows significant increasing trend.

All the indices indicate that high rainfall with shorter duration is increasing for Vadodara city. The observed trends of extreme indices confirm the impact of climate change on rainfall pattern of Vadodara.

Policy makers and town planners should take this impact of climate change in to consideration while planning for flood mitigation, rain water harvesting and disaster management.

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